

HOW TO OVERCOME ATTACKS OF AGGRESSION?

Khaydarova Sarvinoz Saydullayevna

a teacher at the Department of Psychology of
Termiz State University.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7989934>

Abstract. This article is about the aggression of a person in the science of psychology, the origin of aggression and a number of psychological reasons. It is dedicated to the problem of the possible occurrence of symptoms of serious diseases and the research of ways to eliminate the solutions of this problem.

Key words: Aggression, deviant behavior, insomnia, wrong upbringing, psychoses.

КАК ПРЕОДОЛЕТЬ ПРИПАСКИ АГРЕССИИ?

Аннотация. Эта статья об агрессии человека в науке психологии, происхождении агрессии и ряде психологических причин. Она посвящена проблеме возможного возникновения симптомов тяжелых заболеваний и поиску путей устранения решения этой проблемы.

Ключевые слова: Агрессия, девиантное поведение, бессонница, неправильное воспитание, психозы.

Enter. When aggression, like other emotions, is suppressed, a person begins to destroy himself. It accumulates tension, increasing discomfort, and the desire to somehow relieve the tension. A person suffers, suffers, swells, and then suddenly breaks down for some trifle and for some reason, and then (in the case of very deep suppression of aggression) he is even more wounded, and the person leaves with anger sends Often negative innocent people, for example, the house, passengers, subordinates, shop assistants, pets, although the reason for the aggression is completely different, but in this situation there was a prohibition to manifest itself.

Erich Fromm identified two types of aggression: good, which serves to protect one's own interests, property and life, and aggression, which is a pathological pattern of behavior. In the second case, a person can humiliate, insult, fight and put psychological pressure on others in order to raise his reputation. What causes attacks of aggression?

How to deal with them?

Psychologist E. Bass created an expanded classification of aggression. He pointed out that enmity is conveniently divided into two types:

Instrumental aggression. It serves as a means to achieve any goal. For example, my goal is to get on the bus, but all the seats are occupied, and I can argue with someone and it will fall on me. This is a spontaneous hostile attack against a random person;

Targeted (justified) aggression - pre-planned actions aimed at a specific object (revenge on a partner for betrayal; watching the offender return after school; insulting, insulting a person unpleasant to the aggressor). The purpose of such action is to cause physical or moral harm. Documented aggression is often shown by people who grew up in an unfavorable social environment, deprived of normal parents, parental attention and care.

Causes of sudden aggression stranger aggression can occur for a number of psychological reasons, and can also be a symptom of a serious illness.

Psychological omniils include: fast pace of life;

A large number of obligations;

Fatigue, serious problems at work;

Insomnia, severe fatigue;

Wrong education.

An outbreak of aggression can be a symptom of the following diseases:

Brain tumor;

Hormonal deficiency, thyroid gland failure;

Alzheimer's disease;

Post-traumatic stress disorder;

Mental disorders with sudden attacks of violence and imbalance:

Dissocial personality disorder (sociopathy, psychopathy);

Emotionally unstable personality disorder;

Schizophrenia;

Alcoholism and drug addiction;

Psychoses.

Passive aggression in adults.

Uncontrolled attacks of aggression in adults are often caused by constant stress, lack of sleep, fatigue. The body is constantly experiencing emotional and physical stress. Itching intensifies, short temperature appears, imbalance. Often these feelings remain unconscious, and when the accumulated irritation turns into an attack of aggression, a person does not understand why he reacted so sharply.

The flame of anger can be the bright side of decency. From childhood, all people are taught how civilized people should behave, to be obedient and calm. "Are they taking away the car I play with?" I have to give it. You must share!" Such a child becomes an adult with a firm belief that yelling and cursing are bad. If his rights are violated, he will not be able to fight back, but the bad taste will remain in his heart. Protests are growing. As a result, it suddenly appears in the form of incomprehensible and uncontrolled aggression.

Anger and depression are believed to be contradictory and mutually exclusive concepts. However, in fact, in this case, a person is more inclined to the contrary. These feelings stay inside the person, which increases the person's aggression caused by depression.

How to deal with attacks of aggression?

It is necessary to get rid of aggression with peace. You need to tear up a piece of paper, hit a pillow, do a few push-ups or push-ups, and even break a cup, it's not bad.

The main thing is not to harm anyone

Water is very good for relieving stress. You can take a shower or wash the dishes. Anger and anger go a long way in cleaning up. These feelings help you ruthlessly throw away the junk that has been stored for years.

You can go to the stadium and support your favorite team. The main thing is to do it very actively, loudly and emotionally.

Sports are good for getting rid of accumulated bitterness. One is suitable for active activities (running, dancing, football,) and the other is calm and peaceful (yoga, gymnastics). It is necessary to be careful in various types of fighting. For some, things appear this way, for others, on the contrary, a model of behavior "anger - physical aggression" is established.

It is useful to master several methods of relief: meditation, breathing exercises, visualization.

If you feel that you can't control your behavior, don't be afraid to seek professional help. Perhaps the origin of aggression is a symptom of a disease that requires serious treatment.

Emotions belong to the astral plane and arise not as a result of any event, but as a result of the mental evaluation of this event (in different people, the same event can cause different emotions, for example, someone is angry that another car cut, and someone continues calmly).

Aggression in a person occurs due to a reaction to fear or the impossibility of fulfilling a desire. In itself, aggression is not a bad or good thing (appraisals are elements of the mental body, not nervous), it is, like other emotions, tools and signals that allow you to better understand what is happening and control yourself (for example, the body), aggression, in an instant, makes sleepy and physical bodies awake, activity and the ability to perform any serious actions, achievement, overcoming something).

Often, suppression becomes automatic, and a person does not notice this process at all, he almost never gets angry, he does not feel aggression towards anyone, everything in life suits him. In fact, when the first signs of aggression appear, a program is turned on that immediately suppresses aggression and diverts the person's attention by losing consciousness. As a rule, the signal about the presence of aggression does not reach the mind, because the feeling is forbidden from childhood, and a person cannot even admit that he is being attacked.

REFERENCES

1. E.E. Goziev Universal psychology 1 book T.2002 238 p- 89 p
2. M.E. Zufarova General Psychology T. Publishing House of the National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan 2010.-304b-266-p.
3. Smirnova E.O., Khuzeeva G.R. Psikhologicheskie osobennosti i varianty detskoy agressivnosti//Voprosy psikhologii. - 2002. - #1. S. 17
4. Haydarova, S. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF OVERCOMING PERSONAL AGGRESSION. Science and innovation, 1(B7), 1512-1514.
5. JUREVA, S., & MAMARADJABOVA, B. (2020). The degree to which a person feels happy in the family. JOURNAL OF CRITICAL REVIEWS, 7(5), 1873-1875.